

Monday, December 29

Calories

1737

87%

Protein

128.4 g

257%

Carbohydrate

194.7 g

71%

Fat

48.5 g

62%

Cholesterol

593.8 mg

198%

Fiber

18.3 g

65%

Net-Carbs

176.5 g

0%

Saturated Fats

16.6 g

83%

Breakfast

Hard Boiled Eggs

2 x 1 large (50g)

White Bread

2 x 1 slice (29g)

Tomatoes

1 x 1 medium whole (2-3/5 inch dia) (123g)

Raw Carrots

1 x 1 small (5-1/2 inch long) (50g)

Lunch

Soup, chicken noodle, dry, mix

1 x 1 packet (74g)

Cooked Lean Chicken Breast

1 x 3 oz (85g)

Bread, multi-grain (includes whole-grain)

1 x 1 oz (28g)

Dinner

Cooked Pasta (Unenriched)

2 x 100 grams (100g)

Fish, tuna, light, canned in oil, drained solids

1 x 1 cup, solid or chunks (146g)

Swiss Cheese

1 x 1 oz (28g)

Snacks

Pears

1 x 1 cup, slices (140g)

Plain Yogurt (Whole Milk, Full Fat)

1 x 1/2 container (4 oz) (113g)

Blueberries

2 x 1 oz (28g)

Tuesday, December 30

Calories

2836

142%

Protein

106.8 g

214%

Carbohydrate

393.8 g

143%

Fat

93 g

119%

Cholesterol

321.4 mg

107%

Fiber

23.1 g

83%

Net-Carbs

370.8 g

0%

Saturated Fats

29.4 g

147%

Breakfast

Yogurt Fruit Whole Milk

1 x 200 calorie serving (168g)

Cereal Corn Flakes

1 x 200 calorie serving (56g)

Tomatoes

1 x 1 medium whole (2-3/5 inch dia) (123g)

Feta Cheese

2 x 1 oz (28g)

Raw Carrots

1 x 1 large (7-1/4 inch to 8-1/2 inch long) (72g)

Olives

6 x 3 olives (12g)

Lunch

Chicken, broiler or fryers, breast, skinless, boneless, meat only, cooked, grilled

1 x 200 calorie serving (132g)

Tomatoes

1 x 1 medium whole (2-3/5 inch dia) (123g)

Cucumber

1 x 1/2 cup slices (52g)

Mashed Potatoes

1 x 1 cup (229g)

Dinner

White Fish Salad

150 x gm

Davinci - CLASSIC POLENTA

150 x gm

Snacks

Bananas

1 x 1 small (6 inch to 6-7/8 inch long) (101g)

Jam

1 x 200 calorie serving (72g)

Bake crafters - 1702: Pancakes, Whole Grain, Strawberry, 2 Pack. Contains egg, milk, soy, and wheat ingredients. Produced in a nut-free facility.

2 x (74g)

Wednesday, December 31

Calories

1460

73%

Protein

87.5 g

175%

Carbohydrate

182.8 g

66%

Fat

42.2 g

54%

Cholesterol

572.4 mg

191%

Fiber

14 g

50%

Net-Carbs

168.9 g

0%

Saturated Fats

15.9 g

80%

Breakfast

Hard Boiled Eggs

2 x 1 large (50g)

White Bread

2 x 1 slice (29g)

Tomatoes

1 x 1 medium whole (2-3/5 inch dia) (123g)

Raw Carrots

1 x 1 small (5-1/2 inch long) (50g)

Lunch

Soup, chicken noodle, dry, mix

1 x 1 packet (74g)

Cooked Lean Chicken Breast

1 x 3 oz (85g)

Bread, multi-grain (includes whole-grain)

1 x 1 oz (28g)

Dinner

Pizza Cheese With Vegetables Thin Crust

1 x 1 personal size pizza (5-7" diameter) (149g)

Snacks

Tangerines

1 x 1 medium (2-1/2 inch dia) (88g)

Yogurt, fruit, lowfat, with low calorie sweetener

1 x 1 container (6 oz) (170g)

Thursday, January 1

Calories

2315

116%

Protein

97.9 g

196%

Carbohydrate

324.1 g

118%

Fat

78.4 g

101%

Cholesterol

315.2 mg

105%

Fiber

23.4 g

84%

Net-Carbs

300.7 g

0%

Saturated Fats

36.9 g

185%

Breakfast

Yogurt Fruit Whole Milk

1 x 200 calorie serving (168g)

Cereal Corn Flakes

1 x 200 calorie serving (56g)

Tomatoes

1 x 1 medium whole (2-3/5 inch dia) (123g)

Feta Cheese

2 x 1 oz (28g)

Raw Carrots

1 x 1 large (7-1/4 inch to 8-1/2 inch long) (72g)

Olives

6 x 3 olives (12g)

Lunch

Chicken, broiler or fryers, breast, skinless, boneless, meat only, cooked, grilled

1 x 200 calorie serving (132g)

Tomatoes

1 x 1 medium whole (2-3/5 inch dia) (123g)

Cucumber

1 x 1/2 cup slices (52g)

French Fries

2 x 100 grams (100g)

Dinner

Davinci - CLASSIC POLENTA

150 x gm

Swiss Cheese

2 x 1 oz (28g)

Sour Cream

1 x 100 grams (100g)

Snacks

Bananas

1 x 1 small (6 inch to 6-7/8 inch long) (101g)

Apples

1 x 1 cup, quartered or chopped (125g)

Friday, January 2

Calories

2239

112%

Protein

109.7 g

219%

Carbohydrate

345.1 g

125%

Fat

44 g

56%

Cholesterol

616.8 mg

206%

Fiber

20 g

71%

Net-Carbs

325 g

0%

Saturated Fats

12.9 g

65%

Breakfast

Hard Boiled Eggs

2 x 1 large (50g)

White Bread

2 x 1 slice (29g)

Tomatoes

1 x 1 medium whole (2-3/5 inch dia) (123g)

Raw Carrots

1 x 1 large (7-1/4 inch to 8-1/2 inch long) (72g)

Lunch

Soup, chicken noodle, dry, mix

1 x 1 packet (74g)

Cooked Lean Chicken Breast

1 x 3 oz (85g)

Bread, multi-grain (includes whole-grain)

1 x 1 oz (28g)

Dinner

Swiss Cheese

1 x 1 oz (28g)

Fish With Tomato-Based Sauce

1 x 100 grams (100g)

Pasta Shells (Cooked, Unenriched)

2 x 1 cup shells (105g)

Snacks

Strawberries

1 x 1 extra large (1-5/8 inch dia) (27g)

Kiwifruit

1 x 1 fruit (2 inch dia) (69g)

Southern home - PANCAKES

2 x 100 grams (100g)

Honey

1 x 100 grams (100g)

Saturday, January 3

Calories

2153

108%

Protein

85.2 g

170%

Carbohydrate

384.7 g

140%

Fat

71.9 g

92%

Cholesterol

113.9 mg

38%

Fiber

23.1 g

83%

Net-Carbs

346.6 g

0%

Saturated Fats

16.2 g

81%

Breakfast

Yogurt Fruit Whole Milk

1 x 200 calorie serving (168g)

Tomatoes

1 x 1 medium whole (2-3/5 inch dia) (123g)

Feta Cheese

2 x 1 oz (28g)

Raw Carrots

1 x 1 large (7-1/4 inch to 8-1/2 inch long)
(72g)

Olives

6 x 3 olives (12g)

H-e-b - EUROPEAN MUESLI MIXTURE OF CEREALS, DRIED FRUITS, SEEDS & NUTS, EUROPEAN MUESLI

1 x 2/3 cup (66g)

Nuts, acorns, raw

1 x 1 oz (28g)

Lunch

Rice Chicken Cabbage Rolls

3 x 1 (20g)

Davinci - CLASSIC POLENTA

4 x (30g)

Dinner

Davinci - CLASSIC POLENTA

150 x gm

Fish With Tomato-Based Sauce

1 x 100 grams (100g)

Snacks

Oranges

1 x 1 fruit (2-5/8 inch dia) (131g)

Yogurt, fruit, lowfat, with low calorie sweetener

1 x 1 container (6 oz) (170g)

Sunday, January 4

Calories

1825

91%

Protein

106.1 g

212%

Carbohydrate

288.7 g

105%

Fat

30.7 g

39%

Cholesterol

293.5 mg

98%

Fiber

15.7 g

56%

Net-Carbs

272.8 g

0%

Saturated Fats

10.7 g

53%

Breakfast

Yogurt Fruit Whole Milk
1 x 200 calorie serving (168g)

Bananas
1 x 100 grams (100g)

Cereal Corn Flakes
1 x 200 calorie serving (56g)

Lunch

Chicken, broiler or fryers, breast, skinless, boneless, meat only, cooked, grilled
1 x 200 calorie serving (132g)

Cooked White Rice
1 x 1 cup (158g)

Tomatoes
1 x 1 medium whole (2-3/5 inch dia) (123g)

Cucumber
1 x 1/2 cup slices (52g)

Dinner

Fish, carp, cooked, dry heat
1 x 200 calorie serving (123g)

Boiled Potatoes
180 x gm

Local crate - MEAL KIT, SPANISH STEAK SKEWERS WITH SAFFRON RICE & YOGURT SAUCE
2 x 1 oz (28g)

Snacks

Oranges
1 x 1 fruit (2-5/8 inch dia) (131g)

Bake crafters - 1702: Pancakes, Whole Grain, Strawberry, 2 Pack. Contains egg, milk, soy, and wheat ingredients. Produced in a nut-free facility.
1 x 100 grams (100g)

Honey
1 x 1 oz (28g)

Milk Chocolate
2 x 1 bar, miniature (7g)